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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Formulation and *In Vitro* Evaluation of Gatifloxacin Ophthalmic Inserts

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ABSTRACT

Gatifloxacin is a fourth generation fluoroquinolone anti-infective agent useful in the treatment of eye infection such as acute and subacute conjunctivitis, keratitis and keratoconjunctivitis. An attempt has been made to formulate ophthalmic insert of gatifloxacin using hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, methyl cellulose and polyvinyl alcohol as polymers by solvent casting method with aim of increasing the contact time, achieving controlled release, reduction in frequency of administration and greater therapeutic efficacy. The prepared ophthalmic insert were then evaluated for uniformity of thickness, weight, drug content, surface pH, % moisture absorption and % moisture loss. *In vitro* drug release of formulated batches of ophthalmic insert was performed by studying the diffusion through artificial membrane (transparent cellulose type cellophane paper). Out of twelve (F1 to F12) formulations prepared, the formulation F11 containing polyvinyl alcohol (6%) showed prolonged and complete release with 99.06% at the end of 7 hours. The result of *in vitro* diffusion study of promising formulation exhibited first order kinetic, which is non-fickian in nature. The Higuchi plot revealed that the release might be diffusion controlled.

KEYWORDS: Gatifloxacin, ophthalmic inserts polyvinyl alcohol and in vitro release.

INTRODUCTION:

The eye as portal for drug delivery is generally used for local therapy against systemic therapy in order to avoid the risk of eye damage from high blood concentration of the drug, which is not intended. The unique anatomy, physiology and biochemistry of the eye render this organ impervious to foreign substance, thus presenting a constant challenge to the formulator to circumvent the protective barrier of the eye without causing permanent tissue damage¹.

Most of the ocular treatment like eye drops and suspension call for topical administration of ophthalmically active drug to the tissue around the ocular cavity. These dosage form are easy to instill but suffer from the inherent drawback that the majority of the medication they contain is immediately diluted in the tear film as soon as the eye drop solution is instilled into the cul-de-sac and is rapidly drained away from the precorneal cavity by constant tear flow and lacrimo-nasal drainage. Therefore, only a very small fraction of the instilled dose is absorbed by the target tissue for this reason, concentrated solution and frequent dosing are required for the instillation to achieve an adequate level of therapeutic effect. An effective way to achieve slow and prolonged absorption in ophthalmic practice is to incorporate a drug into a polymeric film, which when placed in the cul-de-sac of the eye exhibits a prolonged local release for drug action on tissue in the immediate vicinity².

Gatifloxacin is a fourth generation fluoroquinolone antibacterial agent useful in the treatment of eye infection such as acute and sub acute conjunctivitis, keratitis and keratoconjunctivitis. It is presently available as eye drops. It is administered at dosing interval of 1 drop every two hours in the affected eye. The eye drops types dosage form is convenient to use but most of the drug is diluted by tear and rapidly washed out of the sac by constant tear flow which can be avoided by using insert by which the therapeutic efficacy of ophthalmic drug can greatly improved.³ In the present study, an attempt has been made to formulate ophthalmic insert of gatifloxacin using hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose, methyl cellulose and polyvinyl alcohol as polymers and polyethylene glycol 400 as plasticizer.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials:

Gatifloxacin was obtained as gift sample from Madley pharmaceutical Pvt. Ltd., Daman. Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC 15 cps), methyl cellulose (MC 40 cps) and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) and PEG 400 were obtained from SD Fine chemicals, Mumbai.

Preparation of ophthalmic insert:

The inserts were prepared by solvent casting method. The polymer was dissolved in distilled water and PEG 400 was added as plasticizer to this solution under stirring condition. The weighed amount of gatifloxacin (passed through sieve # 400) was added to above dispersion. After proper mixing the casting solution (5 ml) was poured in clean petridish.

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The petridish was dried at room temperature for 24 h. The dried films thus obtained were cut by cork borer into circular pieces of definite size (8 mm diameter) containing of 1.13 mg of drug and packed in polyethylene laminated aluminium foil. The ocular insert stored in an air tight container below $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ until used.^{4, 5, 6, 15} The formulac for different formulations are shown in the Table-1.

Evaluation of the prepared formulations:⁷⁻¹⁰

Uniformity of thickness:

The thickness of the film was measured at three different spots using digital vernier calipers (Mitutoy, Japan).^{7, 13}

Uniformity of weight:

For uniformity of weight, 3 films from each formulation were taken randomly and their weights were determined using electronic balance.^{8, 11}

Drug content:

Three films were taken from each formulation and dissolved or crushed in 10 ml of isotonic phosphate buffer in a beaker and were filtered into 25 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up to the mark with buffer. One ml of the above solution was withdrawn and the absorbance was measured by UV-VIS spectrophotometer at 285.6 nm after suitable dilutions.

% Moisture absorption:

The percentage moisture absorption test was carried out to check physical stability or integrity of the film at humid condition. The films were weighed and placed in desiccator containing 100 ml of saturated solution of aluminium chloride. After three days, the films were taken out and reweighed. The % moisture absorption was calculated using the formulac⁷

$$\% \text{Moisture absorption} = \frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

% Moisture loss:

The percentage moisture loss was carried out to check the integrity of the film at dry condition. The films were weighted and kept in dessicator containing anhydrous calcium chloride. After three days, the films were taken out and reweighed. The percentage moisture loss was calculated using the formulac⁷

$$\% \text{Moisture loss} = \frac{\text{Initial weight} - \text{Final weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

Surface pH:

The surface pH of the film was determined by allowing them to swell in closed petridish at room temperature for 30 minutes in 0.1 ml of double distilled water. The swollen device was removed and placed under digital pH meter to determine the surface pH.^{9, 10}

In vitro diffusion studies:

The *in vitro* diffusion of drug from the different ophthalmic insert was studied using bi-chambered donor-receptor compartment model^{12, 13}. The commercial semi-permeable

membrane cellophane membrane, presoaked overnight in the freshly prepared dissolution medium (isotonic phosphate buffer pH 7.4), was tied to one end of open cylinder (open at both the side), which acted as a donor compartment. The ophthalmic insert was placed inside the donor compartment in contact with the semi-permeable membrane. The entire surface of the membrane was in contact with the receptor compartment comprising of 25 ml of isotonic phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) in a 100 ml beaker. The content of receptor compartment was stirred continuously using a magnetic stirrer and temperature was maintained at $37^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. At specific intervals of time, 1 ml aliquot of solution was withdrawn from the receptor compartment and replaced with fresh buffer solution. The aliquot was analyzed for the drug content using UV-VIS spectrophotometer at 285.6 nm after appropriate dilutions against reference using isotonic phosphate buffer pH 7.4 as blank.

Release kinetics:

In order to understand the mechanism and kinetics of drug release, the results of the *in vitro* drug release study were fitted with various kinetic equation like zero order(%release vs time), first order(log % unreleased vs time), Higuchi matrix (%release vs square root of time). In order to define a model which will represent a better fit for the formulation, drug release data further analysed by Peppas equation, $M_t/M_\infty = kt^n$, where M_t is the amount of drug released at time t and M_∞ is the amount released at time ∞ , the M_t/M_∞ is the fraction of drug released at time t , k is the kinetic constant and n is the diffusional exponent, a measure of the primary mechanism of drug release. R^2 values were calculated for the linear curves obtained by regression analysis of the above plots¹⁴.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The prepared films were evaluated for the thickness using digital vernier calipers (Mitutoy, Japan). The average of three readings was taken. The mean thickness and standard deviation were calculated. The low standard deviation of the measured thickness of all the 12 formulations ensures the uniformity of the films prepared by solvent casting technique. It was found to be in the range of 0.043 ± 0.007 mm to 0.122 ± 0.005 mm. The weights of all the films were found to be in the range of 1.93 ± 0.035 to 5.33 ± 0.039 mg. For the various formulations, drug content uniformity was found to vary between 1.05 ± 0.060 to 1.11 ± 0.025 mg and the estimation of drug content was found to be almost same with their low standard deviation values.

The % moisture absorption was calculated for all 12 formulations in triplicate. According to the results obtained, the moisture absorption is more in the formulations in which hydrophilic polymers are present. Formulation F4 has shown maximum % moisture absorption, $12.80 \pm 0.50\%$, which may be due to the presence of HPMC which is relatively more hydrophilic in nature.

Table 1: The formulae of the ingredients used in twelve formulations (F1 to F12).

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
Drug(mg)	286	286	286	286	286	286	286	286	286	286	286	286
H.P.M.C. (g)	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
M.C(g)	---	---	---	---	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.35	---	---	---	---
P.V.A(g)	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7
PEG400(g) (30%w/w of polymer)	0.12	0.15	0.18	0.21	0.06	0.075	0.09	0.105	0.12	0.15	0.18	0.21
Water(g)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10

Table 2: Physico-chemical data of various formulations (F1 to F12) of prepared ophthalmic inserts

Product Code	Weight* (mg)	Thickness* (mm)	Drug content*(mg)	% Moisture absorption*	% Moisture loss*	Surface pH
F1	3.20 ± 0.035	0.066 ± 0.005	1.07 ± 0.075	8.05 ± 0.45	13.10 ± 0.75	6.83
F2	3.57 ± 0.062	0.078 ± 0.011	1.08 ± 0.085	9.22 ± 0.62	12.56 ± 0.32	6.76
F3	4.46 ± 0.047	0.086 ± 0.043	1.05 ± 0.060	10.68 ± 0.71	10.27 ± 0.41	7.00
F4	5.33 ± 0.039	0.122 ± 0.005	1.09 ± 0.065	12.80 ± 0.50	9.45 ± 0.95	7.25
F5	1.93 ± 0.035	0.043 ± 0.007	1.08 ± 0.042	7.66 ± 0.59	13.50 ± 0.60	6.90
F6	2.13 ± 0.081	0.061 ± 0.006	1.06 ± 0.071	8.35 ± 0.75	12.12 ± 0.14	7.13
F7	2.40 ± 0.023	0.069 ± 0.007	1.07 ± 0.030	9.43 ± 0.62	11.32 ± 0.53	7.00
F8	2.53 ± 0.042	0.086 ± 0.005	1.10 ± 0.025	10.46 ± 0.82	9.90 ± 0.86	6.60
F9	3.37 ± 0.030	0.051 ± 0.009	1.08 ± 0.045	5.70 ± 0.53	14.10 ± 0.78	6.75
F10	3.58 ± 0.041	0.071 ± 0.007	1.06 ± 0.070	6.72 ± 0.62	13.53 ± 0.34	7.00
F11	3.77 ± 0.046	0.079 ± 0.010	1.11 ± 0.025	7.17 ± 0.36	11.42 ± 0.21	7.25
F12	4.06 ± 0.038	0.094 ± 0.007	1.09 ± 0.069	7.57 ± 0.54	10.35 ± 0.24	7.13

* mean ± SD (n=3)

Table 3: Kinetic data of Drug Release from various formulations (F1 to F12)

Product Codes	Zero order		First order		Higuchi's kinetics		Peppas double log plots	
	Rate constant (K) mg. min ⁻¹	Regression coefficient (R ²)	Rate constant (K) mg. min ⁻¹	Regression coefficient (R ²)	Rate constant (K) mg. min ⁻¹	Regression coefficient (R ²)	Slope(n)	Regression coefficient (R ²)
F1	18.14	0.9207	0.571	0.9710	40.74	0.9340	0.6034	0.9818
F2	15.43	0.9197	0.518	0.9602	40.25	0.9637	0.5795	0.9866
F3	13.19	0.9237	0.424	0.9849	38.44	0.9568	0.5999	0.9839
F4	13.12	0.9579	0.334	0.9807	37.52	0.9474	0.6565	0.9953
F5	22.28	0.8532	0.757	0.9904	40.57	0.9905	0.5678	0.9817
F6	17.60	0.8751	0.581	0.9935	38.90	0.9929	0.5843	0.9852
F7	15.02	0.8808	0.537	0.9960	39.15	0.9869	0.6407	0.9801
F8	15.21	0.9065	0.502	0.9945	40.51	0.9879	0.7000	0.9842
F9	14.86	0.8203	0.607	0.9913	38.51	0.9558	0.4799	0.9993
F10	12.96	0.8788	0.420	0.9942	39.16	0.9713	0.5524	0.9315
F11	12.66	0.9113	0.393	0.9977	36.13	0.9894	0.5180	0.9897
F12	11.68	0.8801	0.306	0.9845	34.91	0.9830	0.5183	0.9443

The formulation F9 has shown the minimum % moisture absorption, 5.70 ± 0.53%, as it contains polymer of less hydrophilic nature. This study has demonstrated that the HPMC and MC have more tendencies to absorb moisture as compared to PVA. At humid conditions, there was more moisture absorption but there was no change in integrity, which was observed by its physical appearance.

The % moisture loss was calculated for all the 12 formulations, in triplicate. The formulation F9 showed maximum moisture loss of 14.10 ± 0.78 and formulation F4 showed minimum moisture loss of 9.45 ± 0.95. The formulations containing PVA had more tendency to lose moisture as compared to those containing HPMC and MC. The surface pH of prepared inserts was found to be between 6.60 to 7.25. That is nearer to the lachrymal pH range.

In the present study, *in vitro* diffusion was carried out in triplicate. At different time intervals, samples were

withdrawn and cumulative % drug release in mg was calculated on the basis of mean amount of gatifloxacin present in the respective film. The percentage drug release of all the formulations is presented in Figure 1, 2 and 3. The ophthalmic inserts prepared with HPMC releases the drug completely in 5 to 7 h. The release of the drug from the formulation F1 and F2 were found to be 98.50% and 99.03% at the end of 5 and 6 h respectively. The release of drug from formulation F3 and F4 was found to be 99.81% and 98.02% at the end of 7 h.

The formulations with MC showed complete release in 4-6 h. The release of drug from the formulation F5 and F6 were found to be 99.15% and 99.35% at the end of 4 and 5 h respectively. The release of drug from formulation F7 and F8 were found to be 99.08% and 97.94% at the end of 6 h respectively.

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The formulations with PVA showed complete release in 6-7 h. The release of drug from the formulation F9 and F10 were found to be 98.85% and 99.86% at the end of 6 h respectively. The release of drug from formulation F11 and F12 were found to be 99.06% and 90.78% at the end of 7 h respectively. Out of 12 formulations (F1 to F12) tried, the formulation F11 containing PVA (6%) was found to be satisfactory, since it showed prolonged and complete release with 99.06% at end of 7 h.

Figure 1: In vitro diffusion of Gatifloxacin from F1, F2, F3 and F4 formulations

Figure 2: In vitro diffusion of Gatifloxacin from F5, F6, F7, F8 formulations

The *in vitro* release data of formulation (F1 to F12) were also subjected to model fitting analysis to know the mechanism of drug release from the formulations by treating the data according to zero order, first order, Higuchi and Peppas equation¹⁴. The results are shown in Table-3. It can be interpreted from the result that the release of drug from the films followed first order kinetics and non-fickian ($0.5 < n < 1$) in nature. Further, the Higuchi plot revealed that the drug release from the inserts obeyed diffusion mechanism.

CONCLUSION:

It can be concluded that the formulation of ophthalmic insert containing gatifloxacin and PVA (6%) seems to be promising and further *in vivo* study must be carried out to check the efficacy of preparations.

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Figure 3: In vitro diffusion of Gatifloxacin from F9, F10, F11, F12 formulations

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